

HTRB effects on threshold instability of 4H-SiC PowerMOSFET with carrots defects

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Abstract

This article presents a reliability study on conventional 650V SiC MOSFETs subject to carrot-like defects under High Temperature Reverse Bias (HTRB) stress. The instabilities of some parameters are monitored, and the drift analysis of the most critical one is presented. The study aims to isolate the impact of carrot defects by comparing devices with these defects to those without and the analysis of the electrical characteristics on samples subjected to HTRB shows an evident difference between devices with and without defects.

1. Introduction

In recent years, silicon carbide (SiC) has become a highly sought-after semiconductor material for automotive applications due to its exceptional physical properties, including a wide bandgap (about 3.2 eV), a high critical electric field (~ 3 MV/cm), and excellent thermal conductivity (~ 280 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹ along C-axis). SiC has emerged as a leading candidate for novel power transistors and high-power density modules [1]. However, being SiC a relatively young material, some failure mechanisms that limit the lifetime of power devices are not fully known and understood. Therefore, research has focused on new protocols and techniques that allow for the qualification of the devices. Among the many issues concerning SiC power devices, particular attention must be given to the challenges related to the epitaxy. In fact, SiC epitaxial layers are often affected by the presence of various kinds of threading dislocations (TDs), with carrot defects appearing to be the most common [2, 3]. Surface morphological defects are usually caused by structural defects inside the material. Several studies have been reported on the carrot defect, and different structures and origins of the defect have been proposed [4-9]. In this context, High Temperature Reverse Bias (HTRB) is one of the routinely performed reliability and qualification tests

in the semiconductor manufacturing industry for 4H-SiC PowerMOSFETs [10, 11]. The HTRB test monitors the leakage current of the devices under high temperature reverse bias conditions over a predefined period of time. Due to the simultaneous application of electrical and thermal stress, this test serves to assess junction integrity, epitaxial defects, and the level of ionic contamination. These aspects can unveil weaknesses or degradation effects in the depletion region at the device's edge termination and in surface passivation.

This study aims to assess the impact of HTRB stress on vertical PowerMOSFETs, specifically comparing devices with inherent defects (referred to as carrot defects) against those without any defects [12]. The analysis of HTRB tests revealed a distinct influence on the Threshold Voltage (V_{th}) between devices with defects and those without. This information is important for developing a methodology to detect defects before the devices completely fail, as it allows for the identification of reliable and reproducible parameters that can be used to detect defects.

2. Carrot Defects

The so-called carrot defect is one of the main

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superficial morphological defects that appear in the epitaxial layers of SiC. Several studies have been reported specifically on the carrot defect, and various structures and origins of the defect have been proposed. However, the formation mechanism of the defect is still not very clear, but as demonstrated by Aigo, T., Ito, W., Tsuge, H. et al., [13], small cavities created during in situ etching before CVD can play a key role in the formation of carrot/comet defects. Generally, this type of defect is due to structural defects and contaminations within the material, as also suggested by the surface morphology of the defect, which usually grows with the increasing thickness of the epitaxial layer. The connection between these defects and TSD (Threading Screw Dislocation) and SF (Stacking Faults) in the substrate or epitaxial layer at their nucleation points is well known [14, 15]. However, it has also been shown that the presence of TSD in the substrate is not always necessary for the nucleation of carrot (or comet) defects, and indeed, the generation of a TSD and a carrot (or comet) defect can occur simultaneously. Another consideration to be made concerns the length of the defect L along the misalignment direction, eq. 1, which is very close to the length of a basal plane in the epilayer when projected onto the surface, taking into account the misalignment angle of the substrate θ :

$$L \approx \frac{d_{epi}}{\tan\theta} \quad (1)$$

where d_{epi} is the thickness of the epilayer. This observation is important because these defects tend to nucleate during the first few stages of epitaxial growth. In case these undesirable defects do appear, the epilayer's thickness can be determined by the defect's size. As compared to the other stacking faults, carrot defects are far more easily seen than any other defect due to an optical microscope. As has been seen from the investigation of several carrot defects, these defects emerge in various shapes, their lengths have fairly uniform values over the whole wafer provided that the epilayer has a constant thickness.

Raman Spectroscopy

A highly useful technique for inspecting carrot or triangular defects is Raman spectroscopy. The Raman measurements were performed using a backscattering configuration, with a 532 nm DPSS laser to excite the sample and a Mitutoyo 100X SLWD objective (NA 0.75) to focus the laser on the sample surface and collect the backscattered signal. The elastically backscattered signal from the sample was removed using Semrock RazorEdge filters placed in the optical

path before the spectrometer. The spectrometer used was an MS350I from Sol, while the detector was an Andor IDUS CCD. This method allows for mapping the stress on the crystal surface, which is proportional to the frequency of the Raman line shifting downward or upward depending on whether the stress is tensile or compressive. Figure 1 (a and b) shows two Raman maps obtained by exciting the sample with a 532 nm laser and mapping point by point the E_1T_0 mode at 777 cm^{-1} of SiC in two different areas of the sample, where various types of defects were observed. Specifically, Figure 1a) presents a comet-like defect, while Figure 1b) shows multiple carrot-like defects. In particular, near the tip of the comet (fig. 1a), the Raman mode at 777 cm^{-1} , is replaced by a mode at 796 cm^{-1} , indicating the presence of a 3C crystalline structure.

Fig. 1: a) Raman map of a 4H-SiC surface populated by a comet-like structure, b) Raman map of a different area of the same sample populated by carrots like defects.

Figure 2 shows the Raman spectra collected at the position marked with the green and red stars on the map (fig. 1a). On the tip of the comet, the mode at 777 cm^{-1} , which is characteristic of 4H-SiC, is replaced by

a mode at 796 cm^{-1} , which is instead characteristic of 3C-SiC [ref1]. Moving from the tail to the tip of the comet, the E_1T_0 mode at 777 cm^{-1} redshifts indicating that the stress is tensile.

The measured shift of the E_1T_0 is about 4 cm^{-1} . Assuming a linear relationship between the shift and stress with a proportionality coefficient of $-0.43\text{ cm}^{-1}/\text{GPa}$ [ref 2], we can conclude that the maximum tensile stress is on the order of 1.7 GPa

When SiC devices include carrot (or comet) defects or triangular defects, the devices show excessive leakage currents and significantly reduced breakdown voltages, as the stacking faults involved in these defects (both in basal and prismatic planes (1-100)) behave as leakage paths. Interestingly, higher densities of carrot (or comet) defects and triangular defects are generated when the epitaxial layers are grown under Si-rich and C-rich conditions, respectively. In fact, under Si-rich conditions, TSDs tend to be deflected in the basal planes, forming Frank-type stacking faults. On the other hand, the migration length of adsorbed species decreases [16, 17] and supersaturation increases under C-rich conditions. The typical density of these macroscopic defects in SiC epitaxial layers is approximately 0.02 cm^{-2} .

2. Device and stress procedure description

The vertical Power MOSFET transistors discussed in this study are produced on 6-inch wafers using an n-type (0001) 4H-SiC substrate, a schematic shown on Figure 2. The substrate has a thickness of $180\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and is doped with $4\text{-}5\text{e}^{18}\text{ cm}^{-3}$ and has a resistivity of $0.012\text{-}0.025\text{ }\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$. A $12\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thick n-epitaxy layer, doped to $8\text{e}^{15}\text{ cm}^{-3}$, is grown on top of the substrate using a warm wall multi-wafer CVD reactor. A 50 nm thick layer of SiO_2 oxide layer is deposited over the epitaxial layer, followed by a Post Oxidation Annealing (POA) using NO as a gaseous

precursor. The inspection at the epitaxy level is performed using Candela 8520 by KLA-Tencor scan, which allowed the detection of surface defects such as droplets, carrots, triangles, micropits, etc. Another inspection is performed at the next level using the KLA Altair inspection microscope, after an appropriate mask that defined the area of the device. This allows us to locate more precisely where any defects fall within the devices present on the wafers.

Fig. 1. (a) Example of schematic of a vertical n-type PMOS structure [Chen, Cen & Ye, Xuerong & Wang, Yixing & Xu, Junzhong & Zhai, Guofu. (2015). PHM application of power converters using health precursor of power MOSFETs. 1-5. 10.1109/PHM.2015.7380078.].

These inspections are important for selecting devices that do not have epitaxial defects, which can be detrimental to device reliability, as shown in Figure 3.

A careful selection is made of good devices that are intended for sale, as well as devices with the presence of epitaxial defects, specifically carrots, which are well-known killer defects [18]. However, even if carrot defects are widely recognized as significant device-killing defects in SiC technology, this study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by providing new empirical data that further quantifies their impact, particularly under HTRB stress conditions. In the high-temperature reverse bias (HTRB) stress test, typically applied on power devices, a percentage of the BVDSS (drain-source Breakdown Voltage, with $V_{GS}=0$) allowed by the data sheet is applied to the body diode with the gate grounded to the source while stressing the device keeping it at a high temperature. The stress time depends on the mission profile. The combined electrical and thermal stress can test the junction integrity of the body diode, crystal defects and ionic-contamination level [L. Anoldo, "Novel idea around wafer level burn-in," Messina, 2019].

While it is true that SiC devices with carrot defects are less desirable from a reliability and

application standpoint, understanding the specific effects of these defects remains crucial. This knowledge can guide improvements in manufacturing processes to minimize such defects and enhance overall device reliability. A large number of devices (100 parts, 50 of which with carrot defects) originating from different wafers are examined to avoid wafer-dependent problems. The devices are thoroughly inspected, and the defects are photographed, as shown in Figure 3 for the reference sample. By selecting both good and defective devices, it is possible to compare and analyse the differences in behaviour between the two types of devices.

Fig. 3. (a) Example of map of the sample processed at the Electrical Wafer Sorting (EWS); in blue the devices that have passed the EWS despite the detected defects such as carrots at an epitaxial inspection and (b) relative photos.

An initial electrical assessment was conducted on the gate oxide and channel leakage current under reverse gate bias. The objective was to identify the initiation of Fowler-Nordheim tunneling conduction and establish stress conditions. Additionally, it was essential to calculate the effective thickness and the active semiconductor doping concentration.

Figure 4 illustrates the gate current characteristics (I_{GS} - V_{GS}) repeated multiple times in both positive and negative polarization regions to determine the stable onset of the Fowler-Nordheim (FN) injection current. This data was also used to identify the gate current initiation and the effective oxide thickness.

Fig. 4. I_G - V_G characteristics of a 500 Å gate oxide on 650 V SiC PowerMOSFET under two consecutive positive and negative bias sweeps at RT for a device with carrots defects (red) and a device without defects (blue).

On the other hand, Figure 5 displays the I_{DS} - V_{DS} characteristics, which were utilized to ascertain the device's operation breakdown voltage (BV_{DS}), semiconductor parameters, and adjust the HTRB stress conditions.

Fig. 5. I_D - V_D characteristics under off conditions on a 650 V SiC PowerMOSFET at RT.

As can be observed, there is a difference, albeit minimal, between the I_D - V_D characteristic of the defective device and that of the defect-free device. This discrepancy is due to the fact that "carrot" defects cause an increase in leakage current in the MOSFET and a decrease in V_{DS} . These defects create weak points where the electric field can concentrate, which could lead to premature breakdown at lower voltages compared to the defect-free device.

In order to study the impact of the stress pattern, the threshold voltage drift is monitored, using a logarithmic readout. Additionally, the characteristic parameters of the MOSFET before and after the stress

test are also monitored. The test protocol is performed using the method schematized in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Block diagram of the stress procedure.

In particular, the transistor Threshold (V_{th}), the threshold with source and drain grounded (V_{ISAT}), the Drain-Source Breakdown Voltage (BV_{DSs}), the Body-Drain diode forward bias (V_{FEC}), the V_{DSs} in ON-state condition (V_{DSON}) and the leakage currents (I_{DSs} , I_{GSs} , I_{Dgo} , I_{Gdo}) are monitored before and after stress. To accelerate the failure of the devices, a V_{DSs} condition near BV_{DSs} (i.e. $V_{DS} = 890 \text{ V} / I_{DSs} \sim 2 \text{ mA}$) is chosen for the HTRB stress. The goal is to keep the transistor in avalanche condition for 500 hours to accelerate the effects of stress. To achieve this, a voltage of approximately 850 V is applied, and the temperature is raised to 200 °C.

The devices are stressed using Infinity QualiTau in HTRB, and the experimental setup is shown in Figure 7.

4. Data/Results and discussion

To simplify the graphical representation of the drift parameter under HTRB stress, a limited selection of devices under test is shown. However, this is confirmed on samples collected from different wafers belonging to different production batches to demonstrate the reliability and reproducibility of the method.

HTRB Test

The goal consists of finding a methodology that can intercept defects before the devices reach a hard

break. This is because, with a view to proceeding with failure analysis, devices that break hard make it difficult or almost impossible to be able to intercept the defect and understand the cause of failure of the device subjected to stress. The V_{th} proved to be a sensitive and useful parameter for our purpose, in fact the devices with carrot defects show a drift of the V_{th} which is much greater than the drift of the devices without defect. The experiment is repeated for a total of 100 samples with defects, of which 50% showed the presence of carrot-type defects, but for ease of reading it is decided to show only the drift of 4 samples. Figure 8 shows the difference between V_{th} measured at time 0, before stress, and its value point by point versus the stress.

Fig. 7. Test setup for HTRB stress: Infinity QualiTau in HCT mode configuration.

It can be noticed that the HTRB stress produced a slight deviation of the threshold voltage $\Delta V_{th} \approx 0.3\%$ from the initial value on the samples without carrot defects (represented in blue) and a large deviation $\Delta V_{th} \approx 13\%$ from the initial value on the samples with carrot defects (represented in red). Moreover, since the carrot defect outside of active region (like Carrot 2 in Figure 3) show a deviation of the ΔV_{th} comparable to the samples without carrot defects, hence the HTRB stress produced a significant degradation only on samples with carrot defects in the

activation area.

Fig. 8. Deviation of Threshold Voltage from initial value under HTRB stress for 2 samples with carrots defects (red) and 2 samples without defects (blue).

In case of devices without carrot defects the deviation in threshold voltage (V_{th}) can indeed occur even in devices that are considered to be free of the specific defects being studied. Several factors can contribute to this variation, including:

- Process variations: differences in the manufacturing process can lead to slight variations in device properties.
- Material inhomogeneities: even in high-quality materials, there can be small inhomogeneities that affect the electrical characteristics.
- Environmental factors: conditions such as temperature and humidity during testing can also impact V_{th}

On the other hand, in case of the devices with carrot defects, this behavior is usually related to negative charges emission or holes trapping in the gate oxide. In more detail, the effect of the negative gate field induced by the HTRB stress condition, which is mainly located in the JFET area, is to deplete electrons with negligible injection of holes due to the small electric field on the p side -body and on the drift of the transistor parameters. Then, under negative field, the holes move through the oxide layer and some of them get trapped in interface traps leading to positively charged centers which results in a lower potential difference, i.e. a lower V will be needed to activate the device. The negative bias stress causes a negative shift in V_{th} which could be explained by the filling and depletion of oxide traps near the interface in the presence of a gate bias stress [19]. Fig. 9 shows a

graphical representation.

Fig. 9. Graphical representation of a cross-section of the structure of a vertical power MOSFET under HTRB conditions. The red arrow represents the movement of electrons, which are pushed towards the source, and the green arrow represents the movement of holes that move towards the drain.

5. Conclusions

The HTRB stress is applied to 4H-SiC PowerMOSFETs that undergo defect-free epitaxial inspection and exhibit satisfactory performance after EWS. Additionally, this stress test is conducted on devices with epitaxial defects, particularly carrots, to assess the drift in the most sensitive electrical test parameters across various sample types. Although the study also refers to “defect-free” devices, it is important to understand that this terminology is relative. In semiconductor manufacturing, achieving absolute perfection is virtually impossible, therefore, “defect-free” generally means that the devices do not have the specific type of defects being studied, in this case, carrot-like defects, or defects that are electrically activated by the HTRB screening test used.

The results showed that V_{th} exhibited greater instability and degradation than the other electrical parameters. This information is important for developing a methodology to detect defects before the devices completely fail, as it allows for the identification of reliable and reproducible parameters that can be used to detect defects. By analysing the drift of V_{th} under HTRB stress, it is possible to assess the impact of stress on devices with and without defects, which is important for ensuring the reliability

and performance of electronic devices.

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